

Kinetics of the Reaction between Lactic Acid and Bromine

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It has been found possible to estimate lactic acid quantitatively by bromine at 35° within a time limit of 4 hours at pH~8 using, at least, 50% excess of the oxidant. The reaction has been shown to be of second order. The temperature coefficient was found to be of the order of 1.26 for temperatures 30°-35° and 1.23 for temperatures 35°-40° and the energy of activation, free energy and entropy of activation was 8.9 kilo cal per mole, 11.4 kilocal/mole-7.9 e. u. respectively at pH~7.60. The reaction rate was found to be maximum at pH~7.60 and decreases on both sides of this value. The inverse dependence of the rate on the concentration of the added bromide shows that the pH effect may be due to hypobromous acid being a faster oxidising agent than molecular bromine as shown by the comparatively fast reaction in bromine free hypobromous acid solution. The reactive species appear to be a combination of hypobromous acid and molecular bromine with $k_{\text{HOBr}} \gg k_{\text{Br}}$ (Tribromide ion being kinetically inactive). The reaction involves a hydride ion transfer and proceeds through the intermediate formation of acetaldehyde.

A SURVEY of the literature revealed that lactic acid has been estimated by different oxidising agents¹⁻³ but no attempt seems to have been made to oxidise lactic acid by bromine and to study its reaction mechanism. Bromine solution (pH~8) oxidises lactic acid quantitatively to acetic acid within a time limit of 4 hrs at 35° using, at least, 50% excess of the oxidant.

The formation of acetic acid as the final product was confirmed through the formation of its acetanilide derivative (m. p. 114°).

Experimental

Materials: All the chemicals used were B.D.H. AnalaR products and were used without any further purification.

Procedure: To 25 ml. of 0.025 molar bromine solution (containing 16 gms KBr. per litre) was added the requisite quantity of buffer which did not have any catalytic effect on the reaction rate. After 30 min. at constant temperature, 25 ml. of 0.025 mol. lactic acid solutions (kept at the same temperature) were added (except in cases of Tables I A and B) and the whole made upto 100 ml. The bottles containing the reaction mixture were covered with black paint to avoid photochemical action. The timer was started during mixing. Samples (10 ml.) were removed at known intervals and to it were added 8 ml. of 1N KI solution and 7.0 ml. N H₂SO₄. The iodine evolved was titrated against 0.05 N hypo solution using starch as indicator. The difference between the two titre values (i. e. of blank and that of reaction mixture) at definite intervals of time represented the amount of lactic acid oxidised at a particular stage. The

hypobromite content of the solution was determined by arsenite method⁴ and used for calculation of rate constants.

Reaction rates: The following tables indicate the nature of results obtained. Graphs were plotted for all results and the specific rate constants k_1 (first order—Table 1 A and B) and k_2 (second order constants using equivalent concentration of reactants—Table 2) obtained from the slopes of log (a-x) and 1/a-x respectively against time.

TABLE 1(A)—(FIRST ORDER CONSTANT WITH RESPECT TO LACTIC ACID)

Hypobromite = 12.50 × 10 ⁻³ M	Temp. = 30° ± 0.05°
Lactic Acid = 0.625 × 10 ⁻³ M	Hypo = 0.01N
Initial pH = 7.20	Final pH = 7.10
	Mean pH = 7.15
$k_1 = 0.50 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$	

TABLE 1 (B)—(FIRST ORDER CONSTANT WITH RESPECT TO HYPOBROMITE)

Hypobromite = 1.25 × 10 ⁻³ M	Temp. = 30° ± 0.05		
	Hypo = 0.001N		
Sodium lactate × 10 ⁻²	2.00	1.25	1.00
$k_1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$	1.7960	1.0940	0.9366
$k_1/\text{sodium lactate}$	0.8960	0.8752	0.9366
Mean value of $k_1/\text{sodium lactate} = 0.9032 \pm 0.0334$			

TABLE 2(A)—(SECOND ORDER CONSTANTS)

Hypobromite = 6.25 × 10 ⁻³ M	Temp. = 35° ± 0.05°			
Lactic acid = 3.12 × 10 ⁻³ M	Hypo = 0.005 N			
k				
No.	Initial pH	Final pH	Mean pH	sec. ⁻¹ mole. ⁻¹ litre × 10 ⁻²
1.	3.20	3.00	3.10	0.015
2.	5.30	4.30	4.80	0.57
3.	6.20	5.10	5.65	1.75
4.	7.35	6.50	6.92	2.59
5.	7.40	6.40	6.90	2.50 (Chloride added 0.1M 25 ml.)
6.	7.50	6.40	6.95	3.15 (Sulphate added 0.1M 25 ml.)
7.	8.00	7.20	7.60	2.61
8.	8.30	7.40	7.85	2.49
9.	9.30	8.40	8.85	1.90
10	11.00	10.80	10.90	1.24
11.	12.00	11.80	11.90	0.10

TABLE 2(B)—SECOND ORDER CONSTANT AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES 30°, 35° and 45° AT pH = 7.60

Temp. °C	k sec. ⁻¹ mole. ⁻¹ litre	Temp. coefficient
30	20.54×10^{-8}	—
35	26.14×10^{-8}	1.26(30°-35°)
40	32.00×10^{-8}	1.23(35°-40°)

TABLE 3

Lactic acid	$= 3.125 \times 10^{-3} M$	Temp. = 35° ± 0.05°
Bromine soln.	$= 6.25 \times 10^{-3} M$	Hypo = 0.005 N
(A) Mean pH = 6.42		
No.	Bromide concentration	k sec. ⁻¹ mole. ⁻¹ litre $\times 10^{-1}$
1.	Nil	0.427
2.	0.2 M	0.170
3.	0.25 M	0.120
4.	0.33 M	0.087
(B) Mean pH = 3.10		
Unbuffered hypobromous acid		k sec. ⁻¹ mole. ⁻¹ litre $\times 10^{-2}$ = 0.266
(C) Mean pH = 8.80		
Buffered hypobromous acid		k sec. ⁻¹ mole. ⁻¹ litre $\times 10^{-2}$ = 1.72

TABLE 4

Experimental Values of Rate Constants at 35°		Calculated values of concentrations at middle stage at 25°		
pH	$k \times 10^2$	pH	$\frac{[\text{HBrO} + \text{Br}_2] \times [\text{CH}_3\text{CHOHCOO}^-]}{\times 10^5}$	$\frac{[\text{HBrO}] \times [\text{CH}_3\text{CHOHCOO}^-]}{\times 1.2 \times 10^5}$
3.10	1.5	2	1.24	1.31×10^{-5}
4.80	57.0	3	11.74	1.13×10^{-8}
5.65	175.0	4	74.29	0.037
6.92	259.0	5	158.96	2.65
7.60	261.0	6	185.29	16.56
7.85	247.0	7	221.66	118.62
8.85	190.0	7.8	251.95	261.55
10.90	124.0	7.9	250.95	263.95
11.90	10.0	8	248.95	265.15
		9	103.99	123.59
		10	19.40	17.88
		11	1.60	1.88
		12	0.16	0.19

Results and Discussion

It has been found possible to estimate lactic acid quantitatively with bromine at pH ~ 8 within a time limit of 4 hrs at 35° using 50% excess of the oxidant when acetic acid was produced as the end product.

The reaction has been studied with a view to identify the actual reactive species and also to ascertain the influence of pH on the reaction rate. The reaction has been shown to be of first order with respect to each of the reactants. Tables (1A and B)—the total order being 2. The results in Table 2(A) indicate that the reaction is fastest at pH ~ 7.60. The effect of addition of electrolytes like Cl⁻ and SO₄²⁻ showed that chloride had no appreciable effect but SO₄²⁻ had a positive effect on reaction rate. However, the rate constant decreases with the increase of bromide

ion concentration which is indicative of the fact that here the reaction with hypobromous acid is faster than that with molecular bromine (Table 3).

The temperature coefficient has been found to be of the order of 1.26 (30°-35°) and 1.23 (35°-40°) (Table 2B). The energy of activation, free energy and entropy of activation were 8.9 kilo cal/mole, 11.4 kilo cal/mole and -7.9 e. u. at pH ~ 7.60.

The reaction rate increases at first with the rise in pH, reaches a maximum at pH ~ 7.60 and then decreases. Experimentally, it has been shown that no complex formation is involved in the system as shown by the plot of 1/k₁ against 1/sod. lactate when a straight line passing through the origin was obtained. The absence of a free radical is indicated by the negative test with mercuric chloride. The fact that the reaction is fast in the alkaline medium (pH ~ 7.60) agrees quantitatively with the assumption that the anion of the substrate is oxidised much more rapidly than the undissociated molecule.

Reactive Species : In bromine solutions, we have $\text{Br}_2 + \text{HBrO} + \text{BrO}^- + \text{Br}_3^- = 3.125 \times 10^{-3}$ (at the middle stage of the reaction)

The results on the effect of addition of bromide ions (in the range 0.2 to 0.33M) showed that the rate constant decreases with increasing concentration of bromide ions (Table 3A).

A graph (based on Table 3A) of the reciprocal of the observed rate constant, k_{obsd} , as a function of bromide concentration C gave a straight line showing that tribromide ion is found to be kinetically inactive. From the slope the value of K₃ obtained was 0.055 which is in close proximity to the value given in the literature⁵ (K₃ dissociation constant of tribromide = 0.056). Now, since Br₃⁻ is not reactive and BrO⁻ is more reactive in strongly alkaline medium (which is not the case, here), we are left with HOBr and Br₂ as the reactive species.

In order to decide which of these two species are reactive, two possibilities⁶ (i) $k_{HOBr} \gg k_{Br_2}$ or (ii) $k_{HOBr} \ll k_{Br_2}$ can now be considered.

On the basis of the first assumption, we get a value of k₁ (k₁ = 22.8×10^{-9}) which is nearer to the accepted value⁷ of 11.3×10^{-9} as compared to the value of k₁ = 130.9×10^{-9} obtained on the basis of the second assumption. Thus, the statement that $k_{HOBr} \gg k_{Br_2}$ is supported by these results.

This conclusion is further borne out by the results with bromine free hypobromous acid (Table 3C). The hypobromous acid was prepared after the method of Knoller and Perlmutter-Hayman⁸.

The reactive species, therefore, appears to be a combination of hypobromous acid and molecular bromine with $k_{HOBr} \gg k_{Br_2}$.

Besides a plot of rate constants (based on Table 2A) against the calculated concentrations of the main reactive species $[\text{HBrO}] \times [\text{CH}_3\text{CHOHCOO}^-]$ at the middle stage of the reaction showed a close parallelism.

Reaction Mechanism : Here, the assumption that both hypobromous acid and molecular bromine act as oxidising agents with $k_{HOBr} \gg k_{Br_2}$ holds good. No test for the formation of pyruvic acid as the intermediate was obtained in this case. The CO_2 produced was tested and estimated which agreed with the reaction involving formation of acetic acid via acetaldehyde. The first step (the oxidation of lactic acid to acetaldehyde), can take place with the help of either HOBr or Br_2 whereas molecular bromine is responsible for the second step (i. e. oxidation of acetaldehyde to acetic acid which is only slowly reacted upon by HOBr) as shown by B. Perlmutter⁹ and also confirmed in these laboratories. In the case of use of hypobromous acid alone, the bromide formed by the reduction of hypobromous acid reacts with the remaining hypobromous acid to liberate an equivalent amount of bromine $HOBr + Br^- = Br_2 + OH^-$.

The reaction can be represented as follows :
 $CH_3CHOHCOOH \rightleftharpoons [CH_3CHOHCOO^-] + H^+$

Since the presence of an α -hydrogen is not a requirement for oxidative decarboxylation, acetaldehyde is formed rather than pyruvic acid.

Here, a hydride ion is transferred from the substrate which is itself oxidised. The formation of acetic acid through the intermediate formation of acetaldehyde suggests that the alcoholic course of oxidation is operative in this case.

The carbon-carbon bond fission is indicated by the production of carbon dioxide (cf. oxidation of glycol or pinacol by periodate¹⁰). The mechanism predicts inversion of configuration and is supported by the optical activity of lactic acid.

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